

Kinetic study of ruthenium(III) catalyzed oxidation of proline by bromate in acidic medium

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Kinetic investigation on ruthenium(III) catalyzed oxidation of proline by acidic solution of potassium bromate in the presence of mercuric acetate as a scavenger for Br^- ion has been made in the temperature range 30–45°. The rate shows zero order kinetics in bromate $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$, but order of reaction is one with respect to the substrate and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ respectively. Increase in $[\text{Cl}^-]$ showed positive effect, while increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ showed negative effect.

Negligible effect of mercuric acetate and ionic strength of the medium is observed. A transient complex, formed between $[\text{RuCl}_6]^{3-}$ and amino acid ($[\text{RuCl}_6]^{3-}$ being reactive species of ruthenium(III) chloride) in 1 : 1 ratio, disproportionates in a slow and rate-determining step. Various activation parameters have been calculated. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Potassium bromate has been earlier used as an oxidant in oxidation of some compounds^{1,2} in acidic media. Scanty attention has been paid to the activity of potassium bromate in the presence of catalyst in acidic media³, but the results have not been interpreted so as to reveal a clear picture of the mode of catalyzed process. The utility of ruthenium(III) chloride as a non-toxic and homogeneous catalyst has been reported by several workers⁴. This promoted us to undertake the present investigation, which consists of "[Ru^{III}] catalyzed oxidation of proline by bromate in perchloric acid medium" and mercuric acetate as a scavenger. Mechanistic steps are discussed.

Results and discussion

Reaction mixtures containing excess of bromate over proline in different ratios were allowed to equilibrate at 35° for 24 h. The stoichiometric analysis of the oxidation reaction of proline with potassium bromate indicates that two moles of oxidant react with one mole of the substrate. Further the product analysis by TLC techniques, indicates the presence of semialdehyde in the reaction mixture, after the reaction. So the product of oxidation should be glutamate γ -semialdehyde.

The overall reaction may be represented stoichiometrically as :

Glutamate γ -semialdehyde
(5-al-2-amino-pentanoic acid)

The kinetic results are presented in Table 1. Zero order rate constants i.e. $(-dc/dt)$ were calculated from the plots of unconsumed bromate vs time. It was observed that the values of $(-dc/dt)$ were constant at all initial concentrations of bromate, showing thus zero order dependence on [bromate].

The kinetic results recorded at various $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$, ionic strengths of the medium along with kinetic effects on successive addition of mercuric acetate, potassium chloride and sodium perchlorate are given in Table 2. First order dependence on $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ is evident from close resemblance between the slope values (1.75×10^{-2} and 3.50×10^{-2} at 35° and 45° for proline) linear plots of $(-dc/dt)$ vs $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ plot and average of experimental k_1 values.

Negligible effects of variation of ionic strength of the medium, addition of mercuric acetate and chloride ions on reaction rate were obvious from the kinetic data (Table 2). Kinetic results obtained on varying the concentration of chloride ions indicate positive effect of chloride ion variation. Change in the ionic strength has only a marginal effect. Kinetic results obtained on varying concentrations of hydrogen ions indicate negative effect of hydrogen ion variation, which means rate constant decrease with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$.

Table 1. Effect of variation of reactants on the reaction rate

$[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{proline}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 35°

[Bromate] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	[Substrate] $\times 10^2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{HClO}_4]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$(-dc/dt)$ proline $\times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.80	0.50	1.00	2.84
1.00	0.50	1.00	2.61
1.25	0.50	1.00	2.55
1.67	0.50	1.00	2.94
2.50	0.50	1.00	3.05
3.30	0.50	1.00	2.97
1.00	0.16	1.00	0.90
1.00	0.20	1.00	1.23
1.00	0.25	1.00	1.52
1.00	0.33	1.00	2.00
1.00	1.00	1.00	5.33
1.00	0.50	0.80	3.00
1.00	0.50	1.25	2.50
1.00	0.50	1.67	2.14
1.00	0.50	2.50	1.90
1.00	0.50	5.00	1.54

Table 2. Effect of variation of chloride ion, mercury(II) acetate and sodium perchlorate at 35°

$[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{proline}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 14.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{NaClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[KCl] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{NaClO}_4]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$(-dc/dt)$ proline $\times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.80	–	1.25	2.19
1.00	–	1.25	2.61
1.25	–	1.25	2.88
1.67	–	1.25	3.16
2.50	–	1.25	3.34
5.00	–	1.25	3.60
1.00	0.80	1.25	2.76
1.00	1.00	1.25	2.61
1.00	1.25	1.25	2.59
1.00	1.67	1.25	2.65
1.00	2.50	1.25	2.70
1.00	5.00	1.25	2.62
1.00	–	0.80	2.44
1.00	–	1.00	2.20
1.00	–	1.67	2.50
1.00	–	2.50	2.42
1.00	–	5.00	2.76

In acidic medium proline exists in protonated form⁵,

The rate was measured at $30\text{--}45^\circ$ and specific rate constants were used to draw a plot of $\log(-dc/dt)$ vs $1/T$, which was linear. The values of the energy of activation (ΔE^*), Arrhenius factor (A), entropy of activation (ΔS^*) and free energy of activation (ΔG^*) calculated from rate measurements at different temperatures are recorded in Table 3.

Mercuric acetate exhibits negligible effect and act as a scavenger⁶ for any Br^- ion formed in the reaction.

$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ chloride has been reported to give a number of possible chloro species dependent on pH of the solution. Under the experimental pH range (1.0–3.0), $[\text{RuCl}_6]^{3-}$ has been confirmed⁷ as the dominant reactive species.

In acidic solution of potassium bromate quick formation of HBrO_3 has been reported². Zero-order dependence on [bromate] suggests that HBrO_3 formed in a fast step, is itself involved in fast step as an oxidant. The results suggest

the following reaction scheme which gives the details of various steps in the title reaction.

Cl^- exists as the following equilibrium⁸ in acidic ruthenium(III) chloride solution. Positive effect with respect to Cl^- in the present investigation suggests that equilibrium would shift to the right. Therefore, $[\text{RuCl}_6]^{3-}$ is the active species of ruthenium(III) chloride media.

where S_1 is heterocyclic amino acid.

where the structure of $[S_1-RuCl_6]^{3-}$ is

$[S_2]$ on hydrolysis forms glutamate γ -semialdehyde⁹.

Now considering the above steps and applying the steady-state treatment with a reasonable approximation, the rate law may be written in terms of rate of consumption $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$ as eq.

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = k_3 [S_1] [\text{RuCl}_6]^{3-} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = \frac{k_3 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} k_1 [\text{Cl}^-]}{(k_{-1} + k_1 [\text{Cl}^-])} \times \frac{[S]}{(1 + K_2 [\text{H}^+])} \quad (8)$$

where $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = C_1 + C_2$, $[S] = S_1 + S_2$ and $K_2 = k_2/k_{-2}$.

The rate law (8) is in agreement with all observed kinetics. The proposed mechanism is consistent with the activation parameters given in Table 3.

Table 3. Activation parameters for acid bromate oxidation of proline
 $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{proline}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 14.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$(-dc/dr) \times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ proline
30	1.78
35	2.61
40	3.70
45	5.12
Arrhenius parameters at 35°	
ΔE^* , kJ mol^{-1}	57.456
$\log A$	10.157
ΔS^* , $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	-12.964
ΔG^* , kJ mol^{-1}	74.226
ΔH^* , kJ mol^{-1}	70.234

Conclusions :

The experimental results as shown reveal that the reaction rate doubles when the concentration of the catalyst $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ is doubled. The rate law eqn. (8) is in conformity with all kinetic observations and the proposed mechanistic steps are supported by the negligible effect of ionic strength, which also explains the involvement of a dipole in the rate determining step. From the present investigation it may be concluded that HBrO_3 and $[\text{RuCl}_6]^{3-}$ are reactive species of KBrO_3 and ruthenium(III) chloride respectively in acidic media.

Experimental

Aqueous solutions of proline, sodium perchlorate, mercuric acetate (all E. Merck) and potassium bromate (AnalaR) were prepared by dissolving the weighed amount of the samples in triple-distilled water. Perchloric acid (60%; E. Merck) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) solution was prepared in HCl of known strength. All other reagents were of A.R. grade. Sodium perchlorate (E. Merck) was used to maintain the ionic strength of the medium. The reaction stills were blackened from outside to prevent photochemical effects.

Kinetics : Requisite volume of all reagents including substrate, were taken in a reaction vessel and thermostated at $35^{\circ} (\pm 0.1^{\circ})$ for thermal equilibrium. A measured volume of potassium bromate solution, maintained separately at the same temperature, was rapidly poured into the reaction vessel. The kinetics were followed by examining aliquots of reaction mixture for potassium bromate iodometrically us-

ing starch as indicator, after suitable time intervals.

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